

A Simple Synthesis of a *cis-anti-cis* Linear Triquinane Framework

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Manuscript received 17 September 1997

A simple approach to the synthesis of a key intermediate containing the *cis-anti-cis* linear triquinane framework starting from readily available indene is described.

The interest in the chemistry of polyquinane natural products has kept the synthetic organic chemists active in the last two decades primarily because of the presence of architecturally pleasing assembly of five-membered rings with various functional groups and the wide ranging biological activity exhibited by some members of the family. These molecules provided the testing ground for a variety of new synthetic strategies for carbocyclic ring construction. Earlier works carried out towards the synthesis of polyquinanes have been extensively reviewed by Paquette¹ and others². The most recent review by Mehta and Srikrishna³ is elegant and impressive and provides insight into more recent developments in this area. Of the natural products bearing a linear triquinane framework, only the thermodynamically favoured *cis-anti-cis* ring fusion has been encountered and the hirsutanes constitute a group of fungal metabolites containing the *cis-anti-cis*-1,4,4,11-tetramethyltricyclo[6.3.0.0^{2,6}]undecane framework (1). The compounds of this family which continue to be of interest to synthetic organic chemists are 2-5 (Scheme 1). In this communication we wish to describe the details of a simple approach to the synthesis of a key intermediate 6 containing the *cis-anti-cis* linear triquinane skeleton.

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

It was decided to use an intermolecular ketene-olefin cycloaddition and Birch reduction followed by cyclization as key strategies to set up the required linear triquinane skeleton as envisioned in the retrosynthetic analysis of intermediate 6 (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

The synthetic sequence adopted is represented in Scheme 3. Accordingly, indene 7 was alkylated with methyl iodide to give a mixture of 1- and 3-methylindenes⁴. The crude product was isomerized by treatment with triethylamine and

Scheme 3 (a) Li, DME, Δ , (b) MeI, (c) $\text{Me} \text{---} \text{C}=\text{O}$, (d) CH_2N_2 , (e) Zn/HOAc , 70° , (f) $\text{HO} \text{---} \text{PTSA}$, benzene, (g) Li, 1,4 NH_3 , EtOH/THF, (h) OsO_4 , *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide, (i) H_2/PtO_2 , (j) $\text{Pb}(\text{OCOMe})_4$, (k) Na_2RuO_4 , (l) $\text{Me}_3\text{O}^+\text{BF}_4^-$, (m) $^t\text{BuO}^-/\text{toluene}$, Δ and (n) HCl/AcOH , Δ

fractionated to obtain 3-methylindene (**8**) in more than 90% purity and in good yields⁵. Other methods of synthesis of **8** gave inferior yields⁶. 3-Methylindene (**8**) was then treated with methylchloroketene generated *in situ* from freshly distilled 2-chloropropionyl chloride⁷ and triethylamine. After refluxing for 2 h in petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) the [2+2]cycloaddition proceeded smoothly and the cycloadduct **9** was isolated in pure form after chromatographic purification in 72% yield. One carbon homologation of **9** was carried out with freshly generated diazomethane to afford the chlorocyclopentanone **10**. Dehalogenation of **10** with zinc/acetic acid⁸ at 70° for 1.0–1.5 h furnished the key cyclopentanone **11** in 98% yield. Before proceeding with the Birch reduction of the aromatic ring the carbonyl group in **11** was protected as the ethylene ketal. Thus ketone **11** on treatment with ethylene glycol in benzene in the presence of catalytic amount of *p*-toluene sulfonic acid yielded the ketal **12** (83%). Lithium/ammonia reduction of ketal **12** in the presence of ethanol as a proton source resulted in the formation of the dihydroaromatic compound **13** in excellent yield (99%). The more easily accessible disubstituted double bond in **13** was then functionalized in a dihydroxylation reaction⁹. Thus treatment of olefin **13** with catalytic amount of osmium tetroxide and 1.1 equivalent of *N*-methyl-morpholine *N*-oxide (25°, 80 h) gave rise to the diol **14** as a viscous oil (78%). Various catalysts (Pd/C, Pt/C, Rh/C) in a variety of solvents (ethanol, ethyl acetate, acetic acid) were tried to reduce the tetrasubstituted double bond in **14**. After considerable effort it was found that activated Adam's catalyst (PtO₂) in methanol at a hydrogen pressure of 50–60 psi for 2 h was the best suited for this reduction and the diol **15** with the desired *cis-anti-cis* basic carbon skeleton could be obtained in 94% yield. In the next stage of the synthetic strategy, the six-membered ring in **15** must be transformed to a five-membered ring. Oxidative cleavage of the diol **15** followed by cyclization will be the obvious choice for this ring contraction. Accordingly, the diol **15** was treated with Pb(OAc)₄ in benzene (25°, 10 min) and the dialdehyde **16** was isolated in 91% yield. Since the dialdehyde **16** was not very stable it was immediately oxidized with sodium ruthenate to the corresponding dicarboxylic acid followed by esterification with methoxoniumfluoroborate¹⁰ to get the methyl ester **17** (82%). Dieckmann cyclization of the diester **17** with potassium *t*-butoxide in toluene followed by acid hydrolysis (HCl/AcOH) gave the key triquinane intermediate **6** (72%).

Although no triquinane natural product has been synthesized, the present report projects a simple and efficient route to a *cis-anti-cis* linearly fused triquinane carbon framework starting from readily available indene.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined with a Uni-melt capillary melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. B.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1320 and 580 spectrophotometers, pmr spectra on Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) and Bruker WP-80 (80 MHz) instruments, chemical shifts being reported in ppm downfield from internal reference tetramethylsilane, and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D 300 spectrometer.

3-Methylindene (8): To a stirred solution of **7** (11.25 g, 101.18 mmol, 11.8 ml) in dimethoxyethane (DME) (100 ml) under nitrogen, was added lithium (0.768 g, 110.68 mg atom) cut into small pieces and refluxed for 5–5.5 h. The dark red solution obtained was cooled in an ice-bath and in methyl iodide (27.26 g, 102.76 mmol, 12 ml) in dimethoxyethane (10 ml) was added over a period of 0.5–0.75 h. After the addition was complete the reaction mixture was stirred for a further 0.5 h. Excess lithium was carefully destroyed by adding 10% HCl (50 ml) and extracted with ether (3 × 25 ml). The ethereal layers were combined and washed successively with water, brine and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate. The crude product obtained after evaporation of the solvent was distilled under vacuum to get a mixture of indene, 1- and 3-methylindene. The product from two such reactions were mixed and refluxed with triethylamine (2 ml) for 2 h. Water (25 ml) was then added and extracted with ether (75 ml). The ether extract was washed with brine and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate. The solvent was evaporated and the crude product obtained was fractionated under vacuum to yield unreacted indene (8.40 g; b.p. 74–75°/11 mm) and 3-methylindene (**8**; 10.98 g, 65%; b.p. 78–80°/11 mm; lit.⁴ 76–78°/11 mm). The purity of 3-methylindene was analyzed by gas chromatography on a Shimadzu GC-9A instrument equipped with a flame ionization detector and a column (2 m, bonded OV-17). Temperature programming was as follows: injection temperature 220°, column temperature 120°/min, raised at 5°/min and isothermal stage at 160° for 1 min; flow rate for N₂ 60 ml min⁻¹, H₂ 50 ml min⁻¹ and air 200 ml min⁻¹, indene *t*_R 2.925 min, 3-methylindene *t*_R 4.42 min; ¹H nmr δ (CCl₄) 2.22 (3H, m, CH₃), 3.27 (2H, t, CH₂), 6.12 (1H, m, =CHCH₂), 7.17 (4H, m).

2-Chloropropionyl chloride: To a stirred solution of 2-chloropropionic acid (40.32 g, 0.371 mmol, 35 ml) and DMF (2 ml) at 85° was added dropwise thionyl chloride (53.042 g, 0.446 mol, 32.5 ml) over a period of 0.5–0.75 h. After the addition was complete, the reaction mixture was stirred at that temperature for 2 h. The temperature was lowered and the product was distilled at atmospheric pressure (100–115°) to yield 2-chloropropionyl chloride (40.15 g, 85%) [lit.⁷ b.p. 110°/744 mm].

3,4-Benzo-5,6-dimethyl-6-chlorobicyclo[3.2.0]heptan-

7-one (9) : A mixture of 3-methylindene (**8**; 2.224 g, 17.11 mmol) and triethylamine (1.90 g, 18.82 mmol, 2.6 ml) in petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°, 80 ml) was gently refluxed. To it, 2-chloropropionyl chloride (2.03 g, 16 mmol, 1.55 ml) in petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°, 16 ml) was added dropwise over a period of 0.5 h. After the addition was over, it was refluxed for an additional 2 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to come to room temperature, and water (20 ml) was added and extracted with ether (3 × 25 ml). The ethereal layers were combined and washed with water (20 ml) and brine (25 ml) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. The solvent was then evaporated and the crude product thus obtained was purified by flash chromatography over silica gel (2% ether in petroleum ether) to recover unreacted starting material **8** (0.7 g). Further elution in 5% ether in petroleum ether afforded the adduct **9** (1.86 g, 72%) as a yellow solid, m.p. 64–65° (Found : C, 70.54; H, 5.68. C₁₃H₁₃OCl calcd. for : C, 70.75; H, 5.89%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3070, 2940, 1780 cm⁻¹, ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.33 (3H, s), 1.75 (3H, s), 3.13–3.24 (2H, m), 3.94–3.99 (1H, dd), 7.23–7.26 (4H, m, ArH); ¹³C nmr δ (CDCl₃) 21.1, 33.1, 33.6, 55.8, 82.5, 125.68, 125.73, 127.5, 128.4, 142.98, 144.2, 206.96; *m/z* 222, 220, 203, 185, 177, 158, 157.

3,4-Benzo-5,6-dimethyl-6-chlorobicyclo[3.3.0]octan-7-one (10) : Diazomethane was generated by the reported procedure from Diazald (4.28 g)¹¹ and added in portions to a stirred solution of **9** (1.86 g, 8.435 mmol) in ether (5 ml) at 0° and then allowed to rise to room temperature. The reaction was monitored periodically by tlc (1–2 h). Excess diazomethane was destroyed by the addition of acetic acid (4–5 drops). Water (20 ml) was added and the layers were separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether (2 × 25 ml). The ethereal layers were combined and washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (10 ml), brine (20 ml), and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. The solvent was evaporated and the crude product thus obtained was used in the next step without further purification, ν_{\max} (neat) 3060, 2930, 2850, 1755 cm⁻¹.

3,4-Benzo-5,6-dimethylbicyclo[3.3.0]octan-7-one (11) : Compound **10** (1.9 g, 8.10 mmol) in acetic acid (14 ml) was treated with zinc powder (4 g) and heated at 70° for 1.5 h. After allowing the reaction mixture to cool to room temperature ether (30 ml) and water (15 ml) were added, and the layers were separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether (2 × 25 ml) and the combined organic layers was successively washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution (15 ml), water (20 ml) and brine (20 ml), and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. The crude product obtained on evaporation of the solvent was purified by flash chromatography (10% ether in petroleum ether) over silica gel to afford the cyclopentanone **11** (1.58 g, 97.5%) as an oil (Found : C, 83.80; H, 7.74. C₁₄H₁₆O calcd. for : C, 84.00; H, 8.00%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3045, 3020, 2960, 2930, 1740 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.07 (3H, d, *J* 7

Hz, CH₃), 1.22 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.3 (1H, q), 2.58 (2H, dd), 2.76 (1H, m), 2.76, 3.31 (H, m, AB-part of an ABX_n), 7.22 (4H, m); ¹³C nmr δ (CDCl₃) 8.1 (q), 22.1 (q), 22.8 (q), 30.1 (s), 35.8 (t), 37.4 (t), 48.0 (d), 51.4 (d), 70.9 (t), 72.8 (t), 122.7 (d), 124.9 (d), 126.4 (d), 126.7 (d), 140.98 (s), 153.4 (s), 219.6 (s); *m/z* 200 (M⁺), 157, 143, 130.

Ethylene ketal (12) : To a stirred solution of ketone **11** (1.72 g, 8.61 mmol) and ethylene glycol (0.58 g, 9.47 mmol, 0.33 ml) in dry benzene (120 ml) was added catalytic amount of *p*-toluene sulfonic acid (20 mg) and refluxed using a Dean-Stark separator. When no more azeotrope formation was observed (1.5 h), saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (20 ml) was added to it and the layers were separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether (25 ml) and the combined organic layers was successively washed with water and brine, and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. The solvent was evaporated and the crude product thus obtained, was purified by flash chromatography over silica gel (ether : petroleum ether, 1 : 9) to get the ketal **12** as a liquid (1.75 g, 83%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3060, 2940, 2870, 1635 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.16 (3H, d, *J* 10 Hz, CH₃), 1.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.28–1.75 (3H, m), 2.0–2.33 (1H, m), 2.73–3.50 (2H, m), 3.94 (4H, m), 7.25 (4H, m); ¹³C nmr δ (CDCl₃) 12.5, 22.7, 30.2, 31.5, 37.8, 39.4, 47.6, 64.7, 65.0, 118.5, 124.98, 125.1, 126.5, 126.7, 143.1, 153.1.

Birch reduction of 12 : Lithium pieces (0.75 g, 107.5 mg atom) were added over a period of 0.25 h to a stirred solution of redistilled liquid ammonia (100 ml). To it, ethylene ketal **12** (1.749 g, 7.168 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (10 ml) and absolute ethanol (0.9 ml) was added and stirring was continued. When the blue colour of the solution disappeared (4 h), solid ammonium chloride was carefully added until excess lithium got destroyed. Ammonia was allowed to evaporate at room temperature. The curdy white precipitate was dissolved in water and extracted with ether (2 × 30 ml). The ethereal extracts were washed with brine until the washings were neutral to litmus and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate. The solvent was evaporated and the crude product thus obtained was purified by flash chromatography (ether : petroleum ether, 1 : 9) to afford **13** (1.73 g, 98.8%) as an oil, ν_{\max} (neat) 3020, 2920, 2870, 1115, 1050 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 0.84 (3H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH₃), 0.97 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.12–1.48 (3H, m), 1.86–2.19 (3H, m), 2.61 (4H, br s), 3.97 (4H, m), 5.8 (2H, br s).

cis-Hydroxylation of olefin 13 with osmium tetroxide and N-methylmorpholine N-oxide⁹ : A mixture of the olefin **13** (1.73 g, 7.02 mmol) and *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide (1.32 g, 11.238 mmol) in acetone (40 ml) and distilled water (14 ml) was treated with a solution of osmium tetroxide (0.178 g in 1.8 ml of tetrahydrofuran, 0.7 mmol) and stirred at room temperature for 80 h. Ethyl acetate (50 ml) and saturated sodium bisulfite solution (5 ml) were then added and the two-phase mixture was stirred vigorously for 0.25 h. The organic layer was removed and the aqueous

phase was extracted with ethyl acetate (4 × 50 ml); the combined organic layers was washed with brine (50 ml) and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate. The solvent was evaporated to afford a green viscous liquid. The crude product was purified by flash chromatography over silica gel (ether : petroleum ether, 1 : 9) to afford the unreacted starting material **13** (0.3 g). Further elution (ethyl acetate : petroleum ether, 7 : 3) afforded the diol **14** (1.27 g, 78%) as a viscous oil (Found : C, 68.42; H, 8.38. C₁₆H₂₄O₄ calcd. for : C, 68.57; H, 8.57%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3500, 2920, 1640 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 0.88 (3H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH₃), 1.0 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.12–1.31 (3H, m), 1.81–2.06 (1H, m), 2.24 (6H, m), 3.25 (2H, br), 3.94 (6H, m); ¹³C nmr δ (CDCl₃) 8.8, 19.5, 30.6, 30.9, 39.6, 39.9, 40.8, 41.8, 45.9, 64, 64.2, 68.8, 69.1, 117.7, 137.9, 138.1; *m/z* 280 (M⁺), 164, 146, 101.

Catalytic reduction of diol 14 : Diol **14** (1.27 g, 4.53 mmol) in dry methanol (5 ml) was added to activated Adam's catalyst (60 mg) in dry methanol (10 ml) and was hydrogenated at a hydrogen pressure of 60 psi for 1 h in a high pressure vessel. The crude product was filtered over a small pad of celite, fresh Adam's catalyst (60 mg) was added, and the hydrogenation was allowed to go for an additional hour at 60 psi. The catalyst was filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated to get a highly viscous oil which was homogeneous to tlc. The crude diol thus obtained was purified by flash chromatography (ethyl acetate : petroleum ether, 7 : 30) to afford the diol **15** as a viscous oil (1.2 g, 94%) which was used in the next step.

Oxidative cleavage of diol 15 with Pb(OAc)₄ : To a stirred solution of diol **15** (0.312 g, 1.1 mmol) in dry benzene (6 ml), was added lead tetraacetate (0.585 g, 1.3 mmol) in small portions and the resulting mixture was stirred at room temperature for 5–10 min. The reaction mixture was then diluted with ether (10 ml) and filtered through a pad of celite and anhydrous magnesium sulfate. The filtrate upon concentration afforded the dialdehyde which was purified immediately over silica gel (ethyl acetate : petroleum ether, 2 : 3) to afford the dialdehyde **16** (0.24 g, 91%) as an oil; ν_{\max} (neat) 2960, 2930, 2720, 1720 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.0 (3H, d), 1.13–1.69 (5H, m), 1.28 (3H, s), 2.14–2.24 (3H, m), 2.38–2.51 (4H, m), 3.9 (4H, m), 9.64 (2H, t); *m/z* 280 (M⁺).

Oxidation and esterification of dialdehyde 16 : A solution of sodium ruthenate was prepared from ruthenium tetroxide (0.27 g, 2 mmol), CCl₄ (6 ml) and 1M solution of NaOH (6 ml). A solution of dialdehyde **16** (0.224 g, 0.8 mmol) in CCl₄ (4 ml) was added to it and stirred at room temperature for 30 min. The crude salt of the dicarboxylic acid was alkylated *in situ* by treatment with trimethyl oxonium fluoborate¹⁰ (0.27 g, 1.8 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (4 ml) at room temperature for 30 min. The reaction mixture was

extracted with ether (3 × 20 ml) and washed with water and brine. After drying over anhyd. Na₂SO₄, the solvent was removed under vacuum to reveal the crude product. It was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (ethyl acetate : petroleum ether, 2 : 3) to afford the diester **17** as an oil (0.223 g, 82%) (Found : C, 63.84; H, 8.14. C₁₈H₂₈O₆ calcd. for : C, 63.53; H, 8.23%); ν_{\max} (neat) 1735 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 0.96 (3H, d), 1.25–1.8 (5H, m), 1.2 (3H, s), 2.1–2.3 (3H, m), 2.5–2.7 (4H, m), 3.75 (6H, s), 3.9 (4H, m); *m/z* 340 (M⁺).

Dieckmann cyclization of diester 17 : To a suspension of potassium *t*-butoxide (0.056 g, 0.5 mmol) in dry toluene (3 ml) was added to a solution of diester **17** (0.170 g, 0.5 mmol) and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The crude product obtained after extraction with ether was treated with a mixture of acetic acid (3 ml) and HCl (3 ml) and refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature, poured into water, and extracted with ether (3 × 20 ml). The ether extract was washed with water, dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and brine. After drying the ether extract with anhydrous MgSO₄, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to yield the crude product. Flash chromatography of the crude product over silica gel (elution with 20% EtOAc/petroleum ether) gave the tricyclic diketone **6** as an oil (0.074 g, 72%); ν_{\max} (neat) 1725 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.1 (3H, d), 1.24 (3H, s), 1.3–1.8 (5H, m), 2.2–2.7 (7H, m); *m/z* 206 (M⁺).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi, for financial support of this investigation and Mr. V. Kesavan for help in the preparation of this manuscript.

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